

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF PERCEPTION OF LEADERSHIP BY HUSBAND AND WIFE IN UZBEK FAMILIES

Umarova Iroda Bakirovna

Guliston State University

Foundation doctoral student

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Abstract. The article presents the results of a study conducted by Uzbek psychologists based on the study of emotional relationships of spouses in families. In addition, the article reveals mutual respect and mutual understanding, as well as trust and problems between the couple in maintaining the stability of family interpersonal relations.

Key words: family, upbringing, relationships, values, research, sympathy, marriage, marital satisfaction, mutual respect, emotional aspiration, mutual understanding.

INTRODUCTION

Without taking into account the national-cultural and socio-psychological characteristics of Uzbek families, it is impossible to properly organize and implement marital relations, family life, its stability and well-being. This condition reduces the effectiveness of its main task - to restore the population by having children, to stabilize the continuity of generations and to ensure the historical progress of mankind, to preserve our traditions and to pass them on from generation to generation.

Leadership in the context of family dynamics is a complex interaction of socio-cultural norms, psychological factors and personal beliefs. Although the concept of leadership in Uzbek families is deeply rooted in traditional values, modern is stabilizing under the influence of socio-psychological factors. Uzbekistan, a country rich in cultural heritage, places great importance on family values and traditional gender roles. Historically, the husband was seen as the primary breadwinner and decision maker, while the wife's role was often associated with housekeeping and raising the family. However, as the social landscape changed, these roles began to evolve, leading to different perceptions of leadership within families. For many Uzbek husbands, the concept of leadership is often related to ensuring financial stability and ensuring the well-being of the family, and they find themselves making important decisions related to the future, education and general well-being of the family. believed to be the protector and provider responsible for making.

Today, educating the young generation and providing them with knowledge about family relations is one of the main urgent tasks. Also, motives determine what constitutes the main needs of young people in preparing them for family life and preventing problematic situations that arise in the process of life.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Uzbek scientists have studied various socio-psychological aspects of the leadership relationship between husband and wife in the family. In particular, YAYakubov was one of the first socio-psychological studies of marital relations in Uzbek families. As the object of the author's research, groups of couples with high indicators of marital stability and couples on the verge of divorce were selected. In both groups, there are differences between spouses' emotional support for each other in performing family functions, socio-psychological characteristics of leadership perception, family values, and guidance on family roles. Based on his research, the scientist noted that the presence of children in Uzbek families and their number is one of the important factors that ensure the strength of marriage. At the same time, characteristics such as traditional, national, family lifestyle, guidance, parental intervention in the relationship of young couples, distribution of leadership in the family, gender equality and their perception by the couple are unilaterally, listed as negative factors, while he evaluated the position of women and their social activity from a positive point of view.

US Saribayeva's work entitled "Effect of sexual-psychological balance on family stability" describes the issues related to the topic of our research. In this work, research was conducted on the sexual-psychological balance of spouses in Uzbek families, the impact of social-psychological features of leadership perception on family stability, and the causes of imbalance.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Although women's issues have been raised to the level of public policy in Uzbekistan, various social or cultural stereotypes and/or barriers still prevent women from achieving equality in work and society, especially in leadership positions. Because the equal participation of men and women in the management system is one of the bright signs of modernization of the society. As an independent subject of international relations, Uzbekistan still fulfills its obligations under major international treaties on human rights.

The higher the level of mutual understanding, emotional closeness and mutual respect in couples, the better their sex-psychological balance and family

stability. In order to ensure family stability, an important conclusion was reached that in order for the couple to achieve sexual balance, it is necessary to increase the level of mutual understanding, emotional closeness and mutual respect [3]. The husband is the head of the family. If a woman respects and obeys her husband, children will also obey their father. As a result, harmony, love prevails in the family and it becomes strong. A woman's disobedience to her husband causes family breakdown and many other unpleasant things. In fact, mutual respect, mutual trust, respect, love, agreement, loyalty and sincerity of relations between a couple serve as the basis for further strengthening of the family.

It can be seen that cultural and traditional values greatly influence husband and wife's perception of leadership in Uzbek families. Uzbek society is largely patriarchal, with men usually considered the head of the family and the main decision-maker. However, it should be noted that there are differences in concepts and practices across regions and individuals. In Uzbek families, the leading and providing role of the land is often emphasized. He is usually expected to make important decisions related to finances, family affairs and foreign affairs. This perception of leadership is deeply rooted in traditional gender roles and expectations, that the husband is the protector and responsible for the welfare and well-being of the family.

On the other hand, the wife's role is often perceived as supportive and nurturing. In Islam, too, a woman is expected to be obedient and respectful to her husband, and her primary purpose is to take care of the home and children. This traditional understanding of leadership often limits the wife's independence in external decision-making.

CONCLUSION

However, it should be noted that there have been changes in recent years. With increasing urbanization, education, and exposure to different cultures, the notions of gender roles and leadership in Uzbek families are gradually changing. Many modern couples are striving for a more equal and supportive partnership, where decisions are made together and both spouses contribute to the well-being of the family. In general, while traditional gender roles and perceptions of leadership still exist in Uzbek families, there is growing recognition and acceptance of a more egalitarian dynamic in which husbands and wives work together as partners in managing their families.

Especially when we talk about gender equality, we can see our women with strong knowledge making effective achievements in any field, entering the

government, school and society. Today, Uzbek women who are working in high-ranking positions are working to raise their children and every young generation in our society in favor of development and contributing to their families.

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